

LEGAL ANALYSIS OF LEGAL PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS OF CHILD VICTIMS OF EARLY MARRIAGE

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Abstract

This study aims to determine and analyze the positive legal regulations in Indonesia regarding the protection of the rights of children who are victims of early marriage and the forms of legal protection for children who are victims of early marriage. This research uses a normative research method with a legislative approach and an analytical approach. The legal sources used are primary, secondary, and tertiary legal materials. The legal analysis will be conducted using a qualitative prescriptive approach. The results of this study are Positive Legal Regulations or Those Applicable in Indonesia Regarding the Protection of the Rights of Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage, namely Law No. 16 of 2019 concerning Marriage (the latest age of marriage is 19 years old, strict supervision and assessment of dispensation requests and children's opinions must be heard in marriage dispensation requests), Law No. 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection (the maximum age of children is 18 years old, affirmation of children, protected children's rights, parental obligations to prevent early marriage and special protection mechanisms as well as recovery mechanisms and criminal sanctions, especially for parents who force children to enter into early marriage) and Law 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence (forced marriage is sexual violence and recovery of children's rights if in early marriage the child becomes a victim according to the provisions of this Law) and Forms of Legal Protection for Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage, namely preventive legal protection (minimum age of 19 years for marriage and the obligation to prevent by parents and the state), repressive legal protection (legal and criminal responsibility for parents or parties who force marriage, the existence of sexual violence and exploitation in early marriage), legal protection in the form of restoration and fulfillment of rights and protection of administrative and civil law (tightening and accuracy in granting marriage dispensations and marriage annulments).

Keywords: *Legal Protection, Rights, Children, Victims, Early Marriage*

INTRODUCTION

Children are part of a vulnerable group whose existence must be guaranteed, protected, and their rights fulfilled by the state, family, and society. From a national legal perspective, children are positioned as subjects who have constitutional rights as stated in Article 28B Paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution which emphasizes that every child has the right to survival, growth and development, protection from violence, and discrimination. This principle is strengthened through Law Number 35 of 2014 in conjunction with Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection, which establishes various forms of legal protection for children in any situation, including when children become victims of early marriage practices.¹ Marriage is a sacred agreement involving a man and a woman who want to continue their relationship to a more serious stage or become a halal relationship, so that they will tie a promise to declare that they are ready to build a household. In relation to the marriage law in force in Indonesia,

¹ Fransiska, N. E., Zukifli Ismail, Ahmad & Melani, P.L. (2021). Textbook of Child and Women's Protection Law. Malang: Mazda Media. P. 23.

according to Law Number 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage, it can be interpreted that: "Marriage is a physical and spiritual bond between a man and a woman as husband and wife with the aim of forming a happy and eternal family (household) based on the One Almighty God."² Early marriage is a social phenomenon that remains a serious problem in Indonesia. Although the government has set a minimum age for marriage, cases of marriage under that age still frequently occur in various regions. This situation has various negative consequences, particularly for children who marry early, who are potentially subjected to violations of their basic rights, both physically, psychologically, and socially.³ However, in reality, early marriage remains widespread in Indonesia and has various impacts on the fulfillment of children's rights. Although Law Number 16 of 2019 raised the minimum age for marriage to 19 for both men and women, applications for marriage dispensations continue to increase in various Religious Courts. This situation indicates that changes in legal norms have not completely eradicated the practice of early marriage, thus increasing the risk of violations of the rights of children involved in such marriages.

According to data from the Ministry of Religious Affairs in 2024, the number of early marriages decreased and was not as high as in 2022 and 2023. In 2024, early marriages involving children numbered 4,150 couples, lower in 2022 at 8,804 couples and in 2023 at 5,589 couples.⁴ However, according to the national statistics agency, although there was a decrease, there was an increase in certain areas, for example West Nusa Tenggara which increased by 14.96 percent from the previous figure.⁵ The high number of underage marriages certainly raises concerns because in general cases of underage marriage end with children dropping out of school and the child's right to receive the education they hope for disappears. According to Ali Imron, early marriage in Indonesia is driven by many factors, such as low family income, low education, and out-of-wedlock pregnancies. Furthermore, evolving cultural and religious values also contribute to early marriage. For example, married women, even as children, are valued more highly than unmarried women. Economic or social factors in a particular region can also force children into early marriage.⁶

Children's rights must be protected and must be prevented from engaging in early marriage because children as the generation and successors of the ideals of the nation's struggle must be protected from all threats and obstacles that exist, because this protection also concerns children's rights, because because of early marriage, children's rights to obtain education or achieve their future are hampered because of early marriage, their rights are neglected and get worse even though a child must be protected in any condition and needs to be given special and humane treatment. Based on the description above, this study will discuss the Positive Legal Regulations in Indonesia Regarding the Protection of the Rights of Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage and the Forms of Legal Protection for Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage.

METHOD

The type of research used is normative research. Normative legal research is also called doctrinal legal research, library research, or documentary study. It is called doctrinal legal research because it is conducted solely on written regulations or other materials. Normative research uses theoretical-rational methods with a deductive logical reasoning model (drawing conclusions from the general to the specific).⁷ The approach used in this writing is the Statute Approach, which is an approach carried out by examining all laws and regulations related to the legal issues being handled and the Analytical Approach, an approach that emphasizes the logical and systematic reasoning process to describe, assess, and construct legal norms, concepts, or events in order to obtain rational legal arguments that can be scientifically justified.⁸ Normative research utilizes deductive logical reasoning. Normative legal research utilizes logical and prescriptive analysis and argumentation. Normative legal research is generally qualitative in

² Tinuk Dwi Cahyani. (2020). Marriage Law. Malang: UMM PRESS. P. 1.

³ Dwi Atmoko & Ahmad Baihaki. (2022). Marriage and Family Law. Malang: Literasi Nusantara Abadi. P. 10.

⁴ Wandu. (2025). Child and Adult Marriage Rates in Indonesia: Social Change and Collective Awareness. Indonesia.GO.ID. <https://indonesia.go.id/kategori/feature/9735/angka-perkawinan-anak-dan-dewasa-di-indonesia-perubahan-sosial-dan-kesadaran-kolektif?lang=1>.

⁵ National Statistics Agency. Proportion of women aged 20-24 who were married or living together before age 18 by province. <https://www.bps.go.id/statistics-table/2/MTM2MCMY/proporsi-perempuan-umur-20-24-tahun-yang-berstatus-kawin-atau-berstatus-hidup-bersama-sebelum-umur-18-tahun-menurut-provinsi.html>.

⁶ Marasaoly, S., Umar, M. H., & Umra, S. I. (2024). Protection of Children's Rights Through Prevention of Early Marriage Among Students in Ternate City. *Journal of Human and Education (JAHE)*, 4(4), 13-18.

⁷ Syarif, M., Ramadhani, R., Graha, M. A. W., Yanuaria, T., Muhtar, M. H., Asmah, N., Syahril, M. A.F., ... & Jannah, M. *Legal Research Methods*. Padang: Get Press Indonesia.

⁸ Juliardi, B., Runtuwuu, Y. B., Musthofa, M. H., TL, A. D., Asriyani, A., Hazmi, R. M., ... & Samara, M. R. (2023). *Legal Research Methods*. Padang: Gita Lentera. P. 21.

nature. Quantitative analysis and argumentation, such as statistical data in tables, diagrams, charts, and images, are also permitted as supplementary (secondary) research materials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Positive Legal Regulations in Indonesia Concerning the Protection of the Rights of Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage

Despite a fairly clear legal framework, the implementation of legal protection for women, especially underage women, during marriage still faces various challenges. One of these is the existence of social and cultural inequalities that lead to male dominance in household structures. This often prevents women from obtaining equal legal protection, particularly regarding economic and social rights. Therefore, in addition to strengthening existing regulations, efforts are needed to change social norms and increase legal awareness among the public so that protection for women, especially underage women, during marriage can be optimally implemented. Early marriage fundamentally contradicts the principles of child protection and the best interests of the child. The negative impacts are not only felt by the individual child but also have implications for the quality of human resources and overall national development. Therefore, the state needs to introduce regulations that can provide effective legal protection for children, especially those who have been or have the potential to be victims of early marriage.⁹

However, in Indonesia's social reality, early marriage remains a common practice, placing children in vulnerable situations. Marriages before a child reaches biological and psychological maturity have the potential to cause various problems, including disruption of a child's rights to education, health care, protection from violence, and opportunities for natural development. Children who become victims of early marriage are often in a powerless position, as marital decisions are largely determined by parents, cultural pressures, economic factors, or specific social norms.¹⁰ As a country based on the rule of law, Indonesia has established various laws and regulations governing the age restrictions on marriage and the protection of children's rights. Children's rights to live, grow, and receive protection are regulated in Article 28 B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution, which states: "Every child has the right to survive, grow, and develop and has the right to protection from violence and discrimination."

The meaning of the above article can be understood that children are subjects of human rights which makes the state obliged to guarantee the right to life, growth, and development of children and have the right to be protected from all forms of violence and discrimination. If in early marriage by the child is seen as threatening the child's health, hindering education and causing physical, psychological, and sexual violence is a practice that is contrary to Article 28B paragraph (2). In addition, Article 28 I paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution emphasizes the right to protection for children from violence and discrimination. The article reads as follows: "Everyone has the right to be free from discriminatory treatment on any basis and has the right to receive protection against such discriminatory treatment." Therefore, understanding the provisions of the above article, in the context of early marriage, children, especially girls, are more vulnerable to becoming victims of early marriage. Therefore, to prevent this, equalizing the age of marriage embodies the principle of non-discrimination and emphasizes that children who marry early should not lose their rights due to their marital status.

Law No. 16 of 2019 in conjunction with Law No. 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage is a form of marriage law reform that was born in response to the high number of child marriages in Indonesia. In addition, it is also due to the Constitutional Court (MK) Decision Number 22/PUU-XV/2017 regulating the different age limits for marriage between men and women Law No. 1 of 1974, by stating that the phrase Article 7 paragraph (1) of the Marriage Law which regulates the age limit for women at 16 years does not have binding legal force. Therefore, in the Regulations in Law No. 1 of 1974 in conjunction with Law No. 16 of 2019 concerning the Protection of the Rights of Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage in detail and completely by regulating and confirming the age limit and tightening the granting or granting of marriage dispensations as a form of government and authorities controlling and preventing the practice of child marriage, protecting children's rights through the judicial process and assessing the physical, psychological and social readiness of children.¹¹ Law No. 35 of 2014 is a strengthening of the child protection regime in Indonesia which aims to guarantee the fulfillment of children's rights as human rights. In addition, it also provides legal protection from all forms of violence, exploitation, and mistreatment and emphasizes the responsibilities of the state, parents, and society. In viewing early marriage, Law No. 35 of 2014 functions as a substantive protection instrument, because it considers child marriage as a condition that eliminates or threatens children's basic rights. The legal regulations in Law No. 35 of 2014 comprehensively protect the rights of children

⁹ Yogi Fahrissal & Haney Fuza. P. (2025). Underage Marriage: Child Protection and Legal Review in Judicial Practice. Lamongan: Detak Pustaka.

¹⁰ Musfiroh, M. R. (2016). Early marriage and child protection efforts in Indonesia. *De Jure: Journal of Law and Sharia*, 8(2), 64-73.

¹¹ Nomenen Sinamo, Hendri Jayadi, Hulman Panjaitan & Parbuntian P. Sinaga. (2024). *Child Protection Law*. Depok: Jala Permata Sari.

who are victims of early marriage, although it does not explicitly regulate early marriage, but in this legislation, the status of children is emphasized, guarantees the right of children to obtain their rights, requires parents to prevent early marriage, requires the state to be responsible for child recovery, and regulates special protection mechanisms and criminal sanctions. In addition, in Law No. 35 of 2014, forced early marriage can be seen as psychological violence against children. From the explanation above regarding the positive legal regulations or those applicable in Indonesia regarding the protection of the rights of children who are victims of early marriage, it can be understood that the statutory provisions that must be seen first are the 1945 Constitution. However, in its implementation, Law No. 16 of 2019 concerning Amendments to Law No. 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage (Confirmation that the minimum age for child marriage must be 19 years, thorough and in-depth examinations regarding requests for marriage dispensation and dispensation for urgent reasons only and the child's opinion must be heard in requests for marriage dispensation), Law No. 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law No. 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection (affirming that 18 years old is still considered a child, protected children's rights, parental obligations to prevent early marriage and special protection mechanisms as well as recovery mechanisms and criminal sanctions, especially for parents who force children to enter into early marriage) and Law 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence (affirming that forced early marriage includes sexual violence that can be punished and the fulfillment and restoration of children's rights if children become victims of early marriage in accordance with the provisions of this Law).

Based on the discussion and explanation above regarding the regulation of Positive Law in Indonesia Regarding the Protection of the Rights of Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage in detail and completely according to the theory of legal protection, namely the 1945 Constitution and the three statutory regulations (the three are Law No. 16 of 2019 in conjunction with Law No. 1 of 1974 on Marriage, Law No. 35 of 2014 on Child Protection and Law No. 12 of 2022 on TPKS) which are the applicable provisions in protecting the rights of children who are victims of early marriage are the efforts of the state or the authorities to protect the interests and rights of children. However, the author's analysis by looking at the perspective of legal protection theory, the three regulations above, (Law No. 16 of 2019 in conjunction with Law No. 1 of 1974 on Marriage, Law No. 35 of 2014 on Child Protection and Law No. 12 of 2022 on TPKS) still have shortcomings in protecting the rights of children who are victims of early marriage. Law No. 16 of 2019 in conjunction with Law No. 1 of 1974 on Marriage still provides marriage dispensation on the grounds that the child has agreed and the absence of strict criteria for "urgent reasons" reduces legal certainty.¹² Meanwhile, according to the theory of legal certainty, positive legal regulations in Indonesia regarding the protection of the rights of children who are victims of early marriage have provided quite strong normative certainty and legal protection for children who are victims of early marriage is clear in normative aspects. However, if viewed from the theory of legal certainty as well, protection for children who are victims of early marriage is still lacking because in these provisions there is no definite criteria for urgent reasons for granting marriage dispensation, there is no special criminal witness and an in-depth interpretation of early marriage in the three laws and regulations. Therefore, according to the theory of legal certainty, legal protection for children who are victims of early marriage in Indonesia has not fully met the ideal principle of legal certainty, although there has been adequate and sufficient improvement.

According to the author, using the theory of justice in assessing positive legal regulations in Indonesia regarding the protection of the rights of children who are victims of early marriage, in Indonesia, the Amendment to the Marriage Law through Law No. 16 of 2019 which raised the minimum age for marriage to 19 years for men and women is a step towards formal and substantive justice. Standardizing the age of marriage eliminates gender discrimination and recognizes that girls and boys have equal rights to optimal childhood and development. However, the existence of marriage dispensations raises serious problems. Marriage dispensations are often granted on the basis of social pressure, customs, or pregnancy, which actually perpetuates injustice against children. In practice, children are not in an equal position to express their free will, so that dispensation decisions tend to ignore the principle of substantive justice.¹³ Meanwhile, Law No. 35 of 2014 on Child Protection has limitations because it does not criminalize early marriage as an act that is inherently detrimental to children. As a result, child victims of early marriage have not fully received justice when their rights are systematically violated.

Forms of Legal Protection for Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage

This legal protection is not only repressive through criminal sanctions, but also preventive, curative, and rehabilitative. Various laws and regulations in Indonesia have regulated forms of child protection, including the 1945

¹² Nur, M., Bukido, R., Subeitan, S. M., Purwadi, W., Usup, D., Isima, N., & Dano, F. (2024). Family Law Counseling: Early Marriage and Protection of Children's Rights in Bolaang Mongondow. *Scientific Journal of Community Service (Nyiur-Dimas)*, 4(1), 1-7.

¹³ Wardah Nuroniyah. (2022). *Child Protection Law in Indonesia*. Central Lombok: Hamjah Diha.

Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection, Law Number 1 of 1974 in conjunction with Law Number 16 of 2019 concerning Marriage, and Law Number 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence (UU TPKS). Legal protection for child victims of early marriage is based on several fundamental reasons. First, children are not physically and psychologically capable, meaning they do not have the mental, emotional, and physical maturity to live married life and household responsibilities. Second, early marriage has the potential to lead to violence and exploitation. Many cases of early marriage occur due to parental coercion, social pressure, or to conceal a pregnancy, which leads to physical, psychological, and sexual violence. Third, it is a violation of human rights against children because early marriage deprives children of their rights to education, health, protection, and participation as guaranteed by national and international law. And fourth, it is the state's obligation to protect children because the state is responsible for ensuring the protection, fulfillment, and respect for children's rights as part of human rights.¹⁴ Prevention efforts are the primary and essential step to prevent early child marriage and reduce its incidence year after year. The following are forms of legal protection for children as victims of early marriage:

1. Preventive Legal Protection

The age limit for marriage in the amendment to the Marriage Law (Law Number 16 of 2019 concerning Amendments to Law Number 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage) is a form of legal protection and prevention efforts so that children do not engage in early marriage without urgent reasons. The provisions on the age limit for children currently in effect are in Article 7 paragraph (1) of Law Number 16 of 2019 concerning Amendments to Law Number 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage which reads: Marriage is only permitted if men and women have reached the age of 19 (nineteen) years. This change in the old law allows men aged 18 years and women aged 16 years to be the minimum age for marriage, but as a prevention effort, there is a new provision that both bride and groom must be 19 years old. This provision is preventive in nature to prevent child marriage.

2. Repressive Legal Protection (Criminal and legal liability)

Early marriage has occurred and in that marriage resulted in a violation of children's rights, then repressive legal protection is needed. Repressive legal protection or Criminal and legal accountability is a form of protection provided after the occurrence of an unlawful act, with the aim of imposing sanctions on the perpetrator, restoring the rights of the victim, and providing a deterrent effect so that similar violations are not repeated. In addition, in early marriage if sexual violence occurs in the relationship, it will be qualified as a criminal act in the Provisions of Law No. 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence (Articles 5 and 6) and in Law No. 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection (Article 76 D).

3. Legal protection in the form of restoration and fulfillment of rights

Legal protection in the form of recovery and fulfillment of rights is a continuation of repressive legal protection for children because children become victims after early marriage. Therefore, the state, as the primary obligation holder, has a constitutional responsibility to not only prevent early marriage but also provide legal protection in the form of recovery and fulfillment of rights for children who have become victims. This protection aims to restore the child's condition to its proper state and ensure the child's survival and future with dignity. Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection stipulates the state's obligation to provide special protection, including physical, psychological, and social recovery. And Law Number 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence (UU TPKS), in which children as victims of early marriage regulate the rights of children as victims in the form of recovery, restitution, rehabilitation, and assistance. If a child becomes a victim of sexual violence in their early marriage, the child will receive special protection.¹⁵

4. Administrative and Civil Protection

In order to protect children who are victims of early marriage, the state provides not only criminal law protection, but also administrative and civil law protection. Both forms of protection are non-punitive and aim to restore the child's legal status, guarantee civil rights, and ensure the responsibility of the relevant parties for the child's welfare. The first administrative legal protection is the regulation and supervision of marriage dispensations, where the court is required to conduct strict examinations of marriage dispensation applications to prevent early marriage. If an early marriage occurs without legal procedures, the state can declare the marriage unregistered and the marriage registrar can be subject to administrative sanctions. In addition, parents can be

¹⁴ Rapitah, R. (2024). Criminal Threats Against Actors in Marriages with Minors in Indonesia. *Ahlika: Journal of Family Law and Islamic Law*, 1(1), 36-57.

¹⁵ Siregar, T. T., Putri, I. R. S., & Gunawan, L. S. (2023). The Role of Human Rights and Customary Law in Preventing Early Marriage in Indonesia. *Innovative: Journal of Social Science Research*, 3(5), 11050-11064.

subject to administrative sanctions in the form of guidance or revocation of certain rights, including restrictions or revocation of parental authority if proven negligent or violent.¹⁶

Meanwhile, civil legal protection, namely in the Marriage Law, provides legal protection for children who are victims of early marriage through the mechanism of marriage annulment, if the marriage is carried out without meeting the age requirements or without court dispensation, then the marriage can be requested for annulment. Because in Article 22 of Law Number 16 of 2019 in conjunction with Law Number 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage states that a marriage can be annulled if the parties do not meet the requirements for carrying out a marriage, such as marriage without permission (coercion), underage without dispensation, or misunderstanding about the partner.

Based on the description above, it can be understood and summarized that the Forms of Legal Protection for Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage are that children must be protected Preventively first by tightening and in-depth assessment in granting marriage dispensation and directly listening to children in marriage dispensation application hearings and also prevention by parents and the state or government for children to marry according to the age stipulated by applicable provisions. However, if the marriage has occurred and in the early marriage that occurs the child experiences psychological, physical and sexual violence, a form of repressive legal protection must be carried out by making parents or parties who force the child or intend to exploit the child in early marriage to be legally or criminally responsible. While other forms of legal protection are recovery and fulfillment of children's rights as victims. Recovery for children as victims includes Psychological, Physical and Reproductive Health and Social Rehabilitation. And the final legal protection is Administrative and civil protection in the form of strict examination in marriage dispensation applications to prevent early marriage and marriage annulment and revocation of parental custody rights if necessary.

The author also sees with the theory of legal certainty that legal protection for children as victims of early marriage in preventive protection with certainty the age limit of marriage in line with Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection which is also in the objectives of Law Number 16 of 2019 in conjunction with Law Number 1 of 1974 concerning marriage, children are only a maximum of 18 years old, indicating that only 19-year-old children are allowed to marry according to applicable provisions and certainly even though it is necessary to marry children early, provisions in Indonesia have the name of marriage dispensation which must be seen for urgent reasons in the court's consideration to grant the request. However, according to the author also The existence of marriage dispensation still creates a space of uncertainty if it is not applied strictly and uniformly by the court even though the rules are certain normatively.¹⁷

Furthermore, in terms of legal certainty, early marriage involving coercion can be categorized as sexual violence under Law Number 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence (UU TPKS). The author views this clear prohibition as fulfilling the principle of legal certainty because it provides a clear boundary between permissible and prohibited acts, while also emphasizing the child's position as a victim, not a perpetrator. Furthermore, in theory, legal protection in the form of restitution and fulfillment of the rights of children as victims of early marriage is certainly possible because it is stipulated in Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection and Law Number 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence.

CONCLUSION

Positive or Applicable Legal Regulations in Indonesia Regarding the Protection of the Rights of Children Who Are Victims of Early Marriage, namely Law No. 16 of 2019 concerning Marriage (the latest age of marriage is 19 years old, strict supervision and assessment of dispensation requests and children's opinions must be heard in marriage dispensation requests), Law No. 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection (the maximum age of children is 18 years old, affirmation of children, protected children's rights, parental obligations to prevent early marriage and special protection mechanisms as well as recovery mechanisms and criminal sanctions, especially for parents who force children to enter into early marriage) and Law 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence (forced marriage is sexual violence and restoration of children's rights if in early marriage the child becomes a victim according to the provisions of this Law). Forms of legal protection for children who are victims of early marriage include preventive legal protection (minimum age of 19 years for marriage and the obligation to prevent by parents and the state), repressive legal protection (legal and criminal responsibility for parents or parties who force marriage, the existence of sexual violence and exploitation in early marriage), legal protection in the form of restoration and

¹⁶ Lujeng P, R., & Sukohar, A. (2016). Domestic violence in cases of early marriage. *Medula Journal*, 6(1), 143-148.

¹⁷ Yuhelson, Y., Sinaulan, R. L., & Rahmat, A. (2020). Social Protection for Women Victims of Early Marriage in Gorontalo. *Journal of Community Empowerment: Media for Development Thought and Preaching*, 4(1), 257-282.

fulfillment of rights and administrative and civil legal protection (tightening and accuracy in granting marriage dispensations and marriage annulments).

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